

ENDOSCOPIC EXAMINATION OF THE UPPER GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT OF CATS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11438196>

Annotation. *The study was conducted to identify pathologies in the upper gastrointestinal tract in cats with diseases of the digestive system. Endoscopic examination was performed on cats with clinical symptoms of digestive disorders. The analysis of the obtained endoscopic data showed that all the examined animals had various degrees of pathology in the upper digestive tract. Cytological studies revealed bile pigments, hematocyte crystals, helminth eggs and spiral bacteria (*Helicobacter* spp.) with a medium and high degree of contamination.*

Keywords: *cats, gastrointestinal tract, endoscopy.*

Introduction. According to statistics, to date, pathologies of the digestive system account for 35% of all diseases in cats. Diseases of the gastrointestinal tract occur in cats of various breeds and age groups. Clinically, these diseases are manifested by emaciation, symptoms of dyspepsia, perversion or complete loss of appetite, soreness during palpation of the epigastric region [1, 2].

Any disorders in the functioning of the digestive system have an impact on the entire body. Digestive dysfunction reduces the effectiveness of nutritional absorption, delays or accelerates the rate of digestion, which can lead to dehydration due to intestinal hyperkinesia or hypokinesia, causing compaction of feces, violation of the acid-base balance of the intestinal microbiome. Increased formation of toxins and their reabsorption into the systemic circulation lead to auto-intoxication of the body, closing a vicious circle of pathological changes [3, 4].

To accurately diagnose and identify the causes of such disorders, veterinary specialists often turn to endoscopic examination of the upper gastrointestinal tract in cats. Endoscopy allows the veterinarian to visually assess the condition of the mucous membranes, detect ulcers, neoplasms, signs of inflammation and other changes. In addition, during the procedure, the doctor can take biopsy samples for histological, bacteriological or cytological examination [5].

The purpose of this study was to establish pathologies in the upper gastrointestinal tract in cats with diseases of the digestive tract.

Materials and methods. This study was conducted on the basis of a veterinary clinic in Kazan. The study included 9 cats with clinical symptoms such as vomiting after eating, vomiting of foreign bodies, loss of appetite. The age of the examined animals ranged from 1 to 12 years: five of which were males and four females.

Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGDS) is an endoscopic examination of the esophagus, stomach and duodenum. This study was performed on cats according to indications for pathologies of the upper gastrointestinal tract. During gastroscopy of the esophagus, attention was paid to the condition of the mucous membrane and the presence of inflammation. When examining the stomach and duodenum, attention was paid to the color, the presence of ulcers, erosions and foreign bodies.

The gastroscopy procedure was performed on 9 animals on an empty stomach in the morning or no earlier than 6-8 hours after feeding. The endoscopic examination was performed by an endoscopist, who performed the manipulation and sampling of the necessary samples. AOHUA VME-5B gastroscope was used, equipped with a light source, a channel for instruments, an air

supply and the necessary manipulators. During the procedure, air was insufflated to better visualize the walls of the gastrointestinal tract and perform the necessary manipulations. If any changes in the mucous membrane were detected, biopsy samples were taken using special forceps for subsequent histological analysis in the laboratory. At the end of the study, air was evacuated from the lumen of the organs, the gastroscope was removed, and the animal was awakened from anesthesia under the supervision of an anesthesiologist.

The results of the study. The conducted EGDS made it possible to visually assess the state of the endoscopic picture of the upper gastrointestinal tract in cats. 9 cats with pronounced clinical manifestations of diseases of the digestive system were subjected to endoscopy. Six cats from this group were sent for cytological examination after endoscopic examination, according to the results of which a preliminary diagnosis was established.

As a result of the study, it was revealed that all the studied animals had typical signs of inflammatory changes in the walls of the digestive tract. The data is presented in table 1.

Table 1. Endoscopic data of the examined cats

Nosoform	Number of sick cats (n=9)	
	Cats	%
Gastritis	4	44,4
Gastroenteritis	3	33,3
Gastroesophageal reflux	1	11,1
Hyperplasia of the cardiac sphincter	1	11,1
Diverticulum of the esophagus	1	11,1
Esophagitis	1	11,1
Foreign bodies in the stomach	4	44,4
Ulcerative erosive process of the duodenum	1	11,1

As can be seen from the presented data, the most common findings during endoscopic examination in cats were pathological changes in the stomach and various forms of esophageal pathology. The results obtained indicate a fairly high incidence of gastric lesions in the examined animals. The data is presented in Table 2, 3.

Table 2. The results of an endoscopic examination of the stomach

Pathological processes of the stomach	Number of sick cats (n=9)	
	Cats	%
Hyperemia	5	55,6
Bleeding	4	44,4
Ulcers/erosions	2	22,2
Swelling of the mucous membrane	3	33,3
A foreign body	4	44,4
Changes in folds	3	33,3

Table 3. Results of endoscopic examination of the esophagus

Pathological processes of the esophagus	Number of sick cats (n=9)	
	Cats	%
Hyperemia	3	33,3
Bleeding	1	11,1

The altered surface of the mucous membrane	4	44,4
Hemorrhagic contents of the esophagus	1	11,1

The data presented in Tables 2-3 characterize in more detail the structure of pathological changes in the stomach (hyperemia in 55.6% of cases, bleeding in 44.4%, swelling of the mucous membrane and changes in folds in 33.3% of cases, ulcers – 22.2% and IT-11%) and esophagus in the examined cats. Most often (in 44% of cases), a change in the surface of the joint was detected, in 33.3% of cases – hyperemia, in 11% - esophageal bleeding and hemorrhagic contents.

However, endoscopy of the duodenum in cats revealed hyperemia and bruising in only one case. Cytological examination was carried out in 6 cats, during which it was found that two animals had bile pigments, 2 had hematocide crystals, one cat had detrid cells and helminth eggs. As a result of cytological examination of smear prints, spiral-shaped bacteria (*Helicobacter spp*) were detected in 2 cases (30%) with a medium and high degree of contamination, in 3 cases bacillus bacteria with a weak, medium and high degree, in two cases cocci bacteria with a low and high degree of contamination.

As a result of microscopic examination, a preliminary diagnosis was made: in five cases neutrophilic inflammation and in one case granulomatous inflammation were detected, which are an indicator of ulcerative defects of the gastrointestinal mucosa.

Conclusion. The data obtained indicate a variety of pathological changes in the stomach and esophagus in cats with clinical symptoms. The revealed changes, including hyperemia, bleeding, the presence of bacteria and other pathological elements, indicate the need for an integrated approach to the diagnosis and treatment of gastrointestinal diseases in animals.

Also, if morphologically characteristic bacteria of the genus *Helicobacter* are found in stomach biopsies of the studied cats, it is advisable to send samples for PCR diagnostics in order to confirm the presence of bacteria. This will allow us to more accurately determine the type and characteristics of the infection, which may be useful for choosing the optimal treatment strategy and controlling the pathology of helicobacteriosis in animals.

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